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Green Amayaga Project and Sustainable Development of Kigoma Sector (2020-2025)

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DECLARATION

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “*Green Amayaga Project and Sustainable Development of Kigoma Sector (2020–2025)*” is my original work and has not been submitted to any other institution of higher learning for any academic award. To the best of my knowledge, all sources used have been acknowledged appropriately through citations and references.

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DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to my beloved family, whose unwavering support and encouragement inspired me to pursue and complete this research. Special thanks to my parents for their sacrifices and constant motivation. I also dedicate this work to the local community of Kigoma Sector, whose collaboration made this study possible.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AFR100	: African Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative
APA	: American Psychological Association
COP	: Conference of the Parties (UNFCCC)
EAC	: East African Community
FLR	: Forest Landscape Restoration
FAO	: Food and Agriculture Organization
GEF	: Global Environment Facility
JADF	: Joint Action Development Forum
MDGs	: Millennium Development Goals
NIM	: National Implementation Modality
NISR	: National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda
NST1, NST2	: National Strategy for Transformation (Phase 1 and Phase 2)
REDD+	: Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation
REMA	: Rwanda Environment Management Authority
SDGs	: Sustainable Development Goals
SES	: Social-Ecological Systems
SFM	: Sustainable Forest Management
SLM	: Sustainable Land Management
UNDP	: United Nations Development Programme
UNFCCC	: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USD	: United States Dollar
VTCs	: Vocational Training Centers

ABSTRACT

This study assesses the contribution of the Green Amayaga Project to sustainable development in Kigoma Sector, Nyanza District, Rwanda. The project, initiated in 2020 as a six-year Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) initiative, was launched to address persistent environmental degradation, biodiversity loss, and rural poverty through a set of integrated interventions including reforestation, agroforestry, soil erosion control, and the distribution of improved cookstoves. The main objective of this study is to assess how the Green Amayaga Project contributes to the sustainable development of Kigoma Sector. The specific objectives are to: (1) examine the socioeconomic benefits of the Green Amayaga Project to local communities; (2) assess the impact of the project on community attitudes toward environmental conservation; and (3) identify the key challenges affecting the project's implementation and sustainability. A mixed-methods approach was employed, involving structured surveys with 97 beneficiaries, key informant interviews, and field observations. The results indicate that the project has had substantial positive effects on household income, energy efficiency, agricultural productivity, and environmental awareness. Notably, over 75% of participants reported increased income and improved food security, while 77% acknowledged benefits from cleaner cooking technologies. These stoves reduced firewood dependency, improved household air quality, and saved time, especially for women and children. The project also promoted a shift in environmental attitudes through tree planting, soil conservation, and sustainable land use practices. However, implementation challenges such as uneven benefit distribution, limited formal training, and incomplete geographic coverage were noted. The study concludes that while the Green Amayaga Project has significantly advanced environmental and socio-economic outcomes in Kigoma Sector, further investment in local capacity-building, equitable participation, and governance mechanisms is essential to ensure its long-term success and scalability.

Keywords: *Project, Amayaga, Green Amayaga, Sustainable Development, Beneficiaries.*

CHAPTER I. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0. Introduction

This chapter discusses the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the research questions, the hypothesis, the research objectives, the methodology, the scope of the study, its significance, and the organization of the work.

1.1. Background of the Study

Sustainable development, first introduced at a global scale by the 1987 Brundtland Report, has become a pressing global concern as the world struggles with issues of environmental degradation, poverty, and inequality. According to the report, sustainable development is defined as the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. (Ozil, 2025) The concept aims to balance economic growth, environmental conservation, and social equity to ensure a better quality of life for the current and future generations.

Over the decades, global efforts to address sustainability challenges have culminated in initiatives like the Millennium Development Goals(MDGs) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals(SDGs). The global discourse on sustainable development has evolved significantly, driven by the escalating recognition of environmental degradation's impact on human well-being. The foundational principle of meeting the needs without compromising future generations ' ability to do the same has been increasingly operationalized through many initiatives like Forest Landscape Restoration(FLR).

The FLR, a strategic approach, aims to restore ecological integrity and enhance multiple ecosystem services in degraded landscapes, contributing to both environmental and socio-economic resilience. (Ha *et al.*, 2022). The Bonn Challenge was launched in 2011 by the International Union for Conservation of Nature, aiming to restore 350 million hectares of degraded land by 2030, and the New York Declaration on Forests of 2014 set ambitious targets for FLR. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) COP conferences have increasingly emphasized the role of forests in climate change mitigation, with initiatives like Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) promoting sustainable development and forest management (UNFCCC, 2022).

Recent studies demonstrate that FLR can significantly enhance carbon sequestration and biodiversity recovery, provided that restoration strategies are context-specific and involve local communities. In

Africa, deforestation and land degradation are worsened by rapid population growth, climate variability, and limited access to sustainable land management practices. (Corbeels et al., 2020). The African Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative (AFR100) aims to restore 100 million hectares of degraded land by 2030, reflecting the continent's commitment to sustainable land management. (Acolatse, 2023)

The EAC Climate Change Policy and Strategy emphasizes the need for integrated approaches to climate adaptation and mitigation, including FLR. Within the EAC, countries face similar issues, and cross-border collaboration for environmental protection is an important part of regional integration. Rwanda, confronting demographic pressures and limited natural resources, has adopted environmental sustainability within its national development strategies, notably Vision 20250 and the National Strategy for Transformation (NST2).

The nation experiences pronounced environmental degradation, particularly in the Amayaga region, characterized by deforestation, soil erosion, and diminished agricultural productivity caused by unsustainable practices. In response to these challenges, the Rwandan government, with support from the Global Environment Facility(GEF) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), initiated the US\$ 32.7 million Green Amayaga Project in 2020. This six-year Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative (2020-2025) aims to rehabilitate degraded landscapes and enhance local livelihoods through forest restoration, sustainable land management, and the promotion of alternative energy sources. This study utilizes Kigoma sector, a rural locale in Nyanza district, as a case study to investigate these dynamics, given its rural state and reliance on agriculture

1.2. Problem statement

The Primary problem facing the Amayaga Region, to which Kigoma sector of Nyanza District belongs, is severe deforestation and subsequent soil erosion primarily driven by unsustainable firewood collection. This has led to depleted farmland, decreased agricultural productivity, biodiversity loss, and limited access to sustainable energy, worsening environmental degradation. (UNDP, 2020). The Green Amayaga Project intervenes through Forest Landscape Restoration initiatives to improve sustainability. However, the actual impact of these efforts on the environment, economy, and society is unclear.

For example, it is unknown if reforestation improves agriculture or community well-being, or if improved cook stoves boost social equity. Furthermore, the project's long-term success relies on local participation, which needs to be better understood. Without proof of tangible benefits, the project's contribution to the

sustainable development of the Kigoma sector remains uncertain. Sustainable development argues that environmental conservation, social equity, and economic development are mutually dependent and should be pursued simultaneously. Forest Landscape restoration (FLR) as a practice relies on the assumption that restoring ecological processes can result in co-benefits to human well-being.

Nevertheless, the literature illustrates that there are intricacies in translating such theoretical links into tangible outcomes. For example, addressing trade-offs between economic growth and environmental rehabilitation and their consequences is not well understood, especially in a resource-poor situation. (Adekunle, 2024). In addition, according to Jiménez-Inchima *et al.* (2021), one of the most controversial aspects of promoting benefit-sharing equity and long-term sustainability is the involvement of residents. Analyzing how the Green Amayaga project handles this complexity and makes it possible to simultaneously achieve environmental, social, and economic goals in a particular local context is therefore a theoretical issue.

While studies have examined the broader impacts of FLR on ecosystem services and livelihoods (Bastin *et al.*, 2019), no single academic article exists that comprehensively evaluates the Green Amayaga project's impacts across all three dimensions of sustainable development. This research gap underscores the need for this study to assess the Green Amayaga Project's contribution to the sustainable development of Kigoma sector. Addressing the gap will provide valuable insights to policymakers, practitioners, and researchers seeking to enhance the effectiveness of FLR initiatives in the Sustainable Development Goals.

1.3. Research questions

1.3.1. General research question

How does the Green Amayaga Project contribute to the sustainable development of Kigoma sector?

1.3.2. Specific research questions

1. To what extent does the Green Amayaga Project affect the socioeconomic welfare of local communities in Kigoma sector?
2. How does the participation in the Green Amayaga Project influence the attitudes of community members towards environmental conservation?
3. What are the challenges of the Green Amayaga Project in promoting sustainable development?

1.4. Hypotheses

1.4.1. Main hypotheses

The main hypothesis of this study is that Green Amayaga has significantly contributed to the sustainable development of local communities in Kigoma Sector.

1.4.2. Specific hypothesis

- **H1:** There is a positive relationship between Green Amayaga Project participation and improved socioeconomic outcomes for local communities in Kigoma sector.
- **H2:** The Green Amayaga Project has led to a positive shift in attitudes towards environmental conservation among participating community members
- **H3:** Limited community participation and poor follow-up significantly reduce the Green Amayaga Project's effectiveness in promoting sustainable development.

1.5. Research objectives

1.5.1. General objective

The general objective of this study is “To assess the contribution of the Green Amayaga Project to the sustainable development of Kigoma sector.”

1.5.2. Specific objectives

1. To examine the socioeconomic benefits of the Green Amayaga Project to local communities.
2. To assess the impact of the Green Amayaga Project on the attitudes towards environmental conservation among participating community members.
3. To identify the challenges of the Green Amayaga Project towards sustainable development

1.6. Research methodology

1.6.1. Research design

The study will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data to measure the Green

Amayaga Project's impacts with qualitative data to understand the community experience. The study will be conducted in Gahombo cell of Kigoma Sector, Nyanza District, Rwanda. The area was selected due to its historical environmental degradation and its inclusion in the Green Amayaga Project's interventions.

1.6.2. Data collection methods

1. Questionnaire: Survey questionnaires will be administered to selected beneficiaries of the project to gather quantitative data on socioeconomic indicators, perceptions of environmental changes, and levels of participation in the project activities.
2. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with local officials and community leaders to gather information on project implementation, challenges, and perceived impacts.
3. Document review: journals, progress reports, and relevant policy documents will be analyzed to understand the planned versus actual implementation of activities.
4. Personnel observations: Direct observations will be made of restored landscapes, agroforestry plots, livestock, and cookstoves to assess environmental challenges.

1.7. Scope of the study

Time scope

This study covers the period from 2023 to 2025, This timeframe allows for assessing the medium-term outcomes of the project interventions.

Geographical scope

This research was limited to Kigoma Sector, specifically in Birambo Village of Gahombo Cell. While the project covers the Amayaga region, focusing on Kigoma sector will allow for a more in-depth analysis of impacts at the local level.

Domain scope

The study focused on three pillars of sustainable development: environment, economic, and social domains. Specifically, it examined how the Green Amayaga Project has influenced these domains in the context of Kigoma sector.

1.8. Significance of the study

This study on the Green Amayaga Project and Sustainable Development of Kigoma sector is significant at personal, academic, and national levels.

Personal interest

This research aligns with my passion for environmental conservation and Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG13 climate action. The study will enhance my research and analytical skills, preparing me for future engagements in policy development, environmental management, and sustainable development.

Academic level

Apart from the mandatory academic requirement to write a dissertation upon the end of undergraduate studies, this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on sustainable development and forest landscape restoration initiatives like the Green Amayaga Project, particularly in the context of Rwanda.

National level

The study is aligned with Rwanda's Vision 2050 and the National Strategy for Transformation (NST1 and NST2), and aims to provide recommendations for enhancing the implementation of green projects, specifically the Green Amayaga Project's effectiveness.

1.9. Organization of the study

This research consists of five chapters: an introductory chapter that provides the background, the statement of the problem, the research questions, hypotheses, the objectives of the study, the methodology used, the scope of the research, the significance of the study, and the organization of the work. The second chapter presents the literature review, summarizing theories developed around the topic and findings from previous research conducted in different geographical areas. The third chapter outlines the methods and techniques used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data. The fourth chapter focuses on data findings, analysis, and interpretation. The fifth chapter discusses the general conclusions and recommendations, including suggestions for further studies.

Summary

This chapter introduces the study by outlining the background of sustainable development and the challenges of environmental degradation in Rwanda, particularly in the Amayaga region. It formulates the

research problem, objectives, questions, hypotheses, and scope. The chapter also explains the significance of the study and describes its overall structure. The Green Amayaga Project is presented as a timely response to these challenges through forest landscape restoration (FLR) and livelihood enhancement. After presenting the general introduction of this dissertation, the next chapter reviews existing literature and theoretical perspectives on sustainable development and forest landscape restoration.

CHAPTER II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0. Introduction

This chapter presents a critical analysis of existing literature related to Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) and sustainable development, with a specific focus on the Green Amayaga Project in Rwanda. The review includes the definition of key concepts, examines empirical studies on the socio-economic impacts of forest landscape restoration, the environmental dimensions, and challenges towards the implementation of FLR for Sustainable Development. It also explores the theoretical foundations of sustainable development and FLR, presents the conceptual framework, and identifies research gaps that the current study aims to address.

2.1. Definition of key concepts

2.1.1 Sustainable Development

Sustainable development, as cited by Ghimire (2023), is the “Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs,” According to Bennich *et al.*, (2023), sustainable development encompasses three interconnected pillars: environmental sustainability, which focuses on maintaining ecological integrity and natural resources; economic sustainability, which emphasizes sustained economic growth without depleting natural capital; and social sustainability, which prioritizes equitable access to resources and opportunity across generations. This multidimensional conceptualization moves beyond traditional economic-centric development models to recognize the interdependence between human well-being and ecological health.

Ghimire (2023) argues that three pillars must be balanced like a three-legged stool; if one leg collapses, the whole system wobbles. Neglect of one derails the others. As a result, integrated approaches that strive to unite ecological, social, and economic dimensions in a holistic and balanced manner become essential to move towards sustainable development.

Figure 1 Three pillars of sustainability by Purvis et al., 2019

The way sustainable development is implemented is not the same as it used to be since its initial conceptualization in the Brundtland Report, with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) providing a comprehensive framework of 17 goals that address various aspects of sustainability. Now, sustainable development is based on the basis of the commitment by each country to achieve each SDG goal. In this study, sustainable development is defined as the enhancement of human well-being, maintaining ecological integrity through balanced environmental, economic, and social interventions.

2.1.2. Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR)

Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) emerged in 2000 as a novel approach to regain ecological functionality and strengthen human well-being in deforested and degraded areas (César *et al.*, 2021). The FLR approach expanded from ecological restoration and reflection upon failures in conservation and forest management approaches, and addresses interventions to recover or conserve native systems. Unlike traditional reforestation that focuses solely on increasing tree cover, FLR emphasizes restoring ecological functions and services while addressing the socio-economic needs of local communities.

According to Mansourian (2020), the FLR encompasses various interventions, including natural regeneration, agroforestry, sustainable land management practices, and community-based forest management. For this study, FLR is viewed as the combination of ecological restoration and livelihood enhancement activities implemented under the Green Amayaga Project. Chazdon *et al.* (2021) argue that

effective FLR initiatives must consider landscape connectivity, biodiversity conservation, ecosystem services provision, and stakeholder participation. For this study, FLR is considered as the combination of ecological restoration and livelihood enhancement activities implemented under the Green Amayaga Project.

2.1.3. Green Amayaga Project

The Green Amayaga Project is a six-year (2020-2025) Forest Landscape Restoration initiative implemented in Kamonyi, Ruhango, Nyanza, and Gisagara districts, which belong to Amayaga Region. According to UNDP (2020), the project represents a US\$ 32.7 million investment funded by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and the United Nations Development Programme in partnership with the Rwandan government. The project aims to address severe environmental degradation in the region, characterized by deforestation, soil erosion, and diminished agricultural productivity (UNDP, 2020).

The Amayaga Project employs multiple strategies, including forest restoration, promotion of agroforestry, sustainable land management practices, and distribution of improved cook stoves to reduce firewood consumption. Wainaina *et al.* (2020) categorize such initiatives as the integrated landscape approaches that simultaneously target ecological restoration and socioeconomic development. For this study, the Green Amayaga Project is defined as a comprehensive FLR initiative aimed at rehabilitating degraded landscapes while enhancing local livelihoods through sustainable practices in the Amayaga region of Rwanda.

2.2. Empirical Review

2.2.1. The socio-economic impacts of forest landscape restoration

The empirical research on the socio-economic impacts of FLR provides mixed evidence regarding their effectiveness in improving community welfare. A study by Djenontin *et al.* (2022) found that smallholder farmers engaged in FLR initiatives often combined multiple land-management practices to achieve specific livelihood, food security, and ecological goals. Similarly, according to Nair *et al.* (2021), the integration of agroforestry is a cornerstone of many FLR projects and can enhance agricultural productivity by improving soil fertility and water availability, while simultaneously providing valuable timber, fuelwood, and non-timber forest products, thereby diversifying income streams for local communities.

Moluh Njoya *et al* (2025) found that smallholder farmers who practiced agroforestry, soil conservation, and similar techniques were able to restore land while also boosting their productivity. But not everyone has the same ability to take part. The study found that farmers who had secure access to land, were financially stable, and had access to training or extension services were more likely to adopt these practices and stick with them. In other words, if you give farmers the tools, knowledge, and confidence that their efforts will pay off, they are much more likely to invest in restoring their land.

Furthermore, according to César *et al* (2021), FLR can promote economic diversification by integrating income-generating activities such as non-timber forest product harvesting, eco-tourism, and sustainable agriculture. Employment opportunities can also be found in tree planting, nursery operations, and restoration tracking. This is especially important in areas where traditional farming alone might not be enough to support a household. César *et al* (2021) and Moluh Njoya *et al* (2025) cited the significance of FLR projects towards social outcomes, particularly when designed and implemented with community participation in mind. Restoration works tend to do more than just fix the environment, they bring people together. In many areas, local involvement helped foster trust, improve cooperation, and empower people to take more control over the land they depend on.

Loireng and Kimaru (2023) also highlight that reforestation efforts, driven by the need to reclaim degraded forests, can lead to improved livelihoods, clean water, sustainable food production, and climate change reduction. The study emphasizes the importance of community involvement in forest management and the potential for socio-economic benefits to incentivize participation in conservation practices. However, Noulèkoun *et al.* (2021) argue that FLR implementation is often challenged by a lack of clarity in governance structures, especially across transboundary landscapes. Where governance is weak, the socio-economic benefits of FLR may not be equitably distributed, consequently reinforcing existing inequalities. Therefore, unlocking the social and economic benefits should take thoughtful planning and a genuine commitment to equity from the very beginning.

2.2.2. Environmental conservation attitudes and practices

Mansourian *et al* (2024) stress how vital it is to understand the relationship between people and forests is crucial for successful Forest Landscape Restoration. The author highlights that humans depend on forests, can harm them, and also work to restore them, and all these actions have impacts on us. The study provides a framework and practical advice for bringing these human aspects into forest restoration efforts. This

means acknowledging the complex relationship between nature and society, and taking practical steps to include people's needs and activities in restoration projects.

The study by Deville *et al.* (2021) shows that the more direct experiences individuals have in natural settings, the more likely they are to develop positive attitudes toward conservation and adopt eco-friendly behaviors. Furthermore, Ihemezie *et al.* (2021) conducted a systematic review of the literature and concluded that human values have a significant influence on attitudes and behaviors towards forest conservation. In other words, what people believe is important to them (their values) strongly influences whether they care about saving forests and what they do to help (or hurt) conservation efforts.

2.2.3. Challenges in implementing FLR for sustainable development

The most significant barrier to FLR implementation is the lack of integrated and coherent policy frameworks. agencies overlap forest restoration programs without coordination, often targeting the same degraded landscapes. FLR is not just about planting trees. It is a broad approach that considers ecological, social, and economic dimensions. This requires input and alignment across various sectors like forestry, agriculture, water management, energy, land tenure, and even social development. This siloed approach leads to inefficiencies and conflicts in land use planning and implementation (A. *et al.*, 2022).

The FLR is participatory in nature. However, insufficient engagement, limited recognition of customary land rights, and inadequate benefits-sharing mechanisms weaken community ownership as well as participation. Empirical evidence suggests that when local stakeholders lack secure land tenure or perceive minimal direct benefits, their motivation to participate in restoration activities diminishes significantly (Kassa *et al.*, 2022). Also the above is coupled with conflicting objectives for concerned parties make it difficult for the needed intervention to solve these problems.

Moreover, despite the increasing global commitments, financing remains a critical bottleneck for scaling up FLR initiatives. The Economics of Ecosystem Restoration Initiative estimates that meeting global restoration would require between \$300 billion and 350 billion annually, yet the actual investments fall drastically short of this figure (FAO and UNEP, 2020). This funding gap is particularly severe in low-income countries with high restoration potential. Erbaugh *et al.* (2020) found that many initiatives struggle to develop sustainable business models that can persist beyond donor funding cycles.

Failure to have viable plans for financial self-sufficiency creates extreme dependency on external funding, and this creates vulnerability and often leads to project abandonment when the initial source of funds

expires. However, when looking at the local context, access to finance becomes very difficult for small, medium, and community-based restoration efforts. This makes it hard when it comes to the needed technical knowledge and building operational capacity.

Chazdon *et al* (2020) highlight that the shortage of expertise, infrastructure limitations, and inadequate monitoring capacity affect large-scale global restoration efforts. The study also cited that technical capacity and decision support tools in many developing countries are insufficient to initiate, implement, and sustain effective FLR. They further recommend that expertise in large-scale tree-planting initiatives based on monocultures or exotic species, accessible and evidence-based guidelines regarding collecting baseline data, visioning landscape options, defining landscape boundaries, selecting appropriate tree species, and monitoring indicators are urgently needed.

2.3. Theoretical Review

This section presents the theoretical foundations that underpin the study on Green Amayaga Project and sustainable development in Kigoma Sector. The research is guided by three complementary theoretical frameworks that provide analytical lenses for understanding the complex dynamics of Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) and sustainable development: Social-Ecological Systems Theory, Environmental Stewardship Theory, and Sustainable Livelihoods Framework.

2.3.1. Social-Ecological Systems (SES) Theory

The Socio-Ecological Systems theory provides a framework for understanding the interdependence between human activities and ecological processes in landscapes undergoing restoration. This theory recognizes that human and natural systems are intricately connected and cannot be analyzed in isolation. In the context of the Green Amayaga Project, the SES theory helps understand how social and ecological components interact across multiple scales and how these interactions influence restoration outcomes.

Folke *et al.* (2021) argue that sustainable management of forests requires understanding the complex feedback mechanisms between social and ecological subsystems. They emphasize that resilience in social-ecological systems emerges from adaptability and transformation in response to disturbance. Viewed from its design, the Green Amayaga Project is rehabilitating degraded landscapes while simultaneously improving local livelihoods. This dual focus positions the project as an intervention within a broader social-ecological system (SES), where human well-being and ecological integrity are deeply interlinked.

In light of the Green Amayaga Project, the SES framework should be understood as engaging multiple subsystems. These are resource systems: forested landscapes, resource units (soil, water, biodiversity), users (local communities, Kigoma community), and governance systems (local institutions, policies). The collectivity of these systems determines the effectiveness of restoration initiatives.

2.3.2. Environmental Stewardship Theory

Bennett *et al* (2021a) define the concept of environmental stewardship as the actions taken by individuals, groups, and networks to protect, care for, or responsibly use the environment in pursuit of environmental and/or social outcomes in diverse social-ecological contexts. This view aligns with the Green Amayaga Project in the Kigoma Sector, which similarly seeks to restore degraded landscapes and local livelihoods. It is allowing communities to re-create the environment and the future for their communities by planting trees, practicing sustainable farming, and conserving soil.

We can view their reasons for participating in these initiatives- the expectation of improved harvests, the importance of traditional knowledge, the wish for a healthy environment to hand to the next generations- all through the lens of stewardship. As Bennett *et al* (2021b) argue, progress is only achieved when “communities are more than included, that is, they are empowered to lead”. Similarly, for the Green Amayaga Project, the future of the project relies on whether people feel that they have ownership and responsibility of the land. As environmental stewardship theory reminds us, sustainable development is not merely policies and programs, it is about people and the values they hold and how they relate to the environment that they call home.

2.3.3. Sustainable Livelihoods Framework

The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework provides insight into how people in rural communities, such as Kigoma Sector, navigate their daily life and make a living within things like restoration projects such as Green Amayaga. This perspective examines how families use their assets, such as their land, tools, savings, skills, knowledge, and community networks, to develop strategies for resilience in the face of droughts, market shifts, and other unforeseen problems. The core of this framework is the understanding that people don't receive aid or environmental programs, but rather actively decision-making individuals with their priorities, strengths, and strategies.

Erbaugh *et al.* (2020) highlight how the most effective forest restoration “understands that addressing multiple facets of people’s lives simultaneously is most productive”. Therefore, the introduction of agroforestry or improved cook stoves as part of the Green Amayaga Project in the Kigoma Sector does not only mean an attempt to restore the landscape, but has the potential to change how families generate income, prepare food, and think about their futures. That perspective is helpful when assessing Green Amayaga's work in Kigoma Sector, as it allows us to move beyond planting trees as a numerical measure.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

According to Villeneuve (2024), Anfara and Mertz define a conceptual framework as a lens through which the researcher views the problem, its context, and its possible solutions, guided by theory and supported by existing literature. It helps to identify what to study, what data to collect, and how to interpret findings. This conceptual framework therefore provides a structure for evaluating the Green Amayaga Project’s contribution to sustainable development, recognizing the interdependence of ecological, social systems, and livelihood outcomes.

Figure 2. Conceptual framework of the study

Source: Compilation of the researcher May, 2025

2.5. Synthesis and research gap

Despite the growing body of research on Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) and sustainable development, several critical gaps persist, particularly within the Rwandan context and specifically concerning the Green Amayaga Project. First, although empirical studies have examined the socio-economic and environmental impacts of FLR initiatives globally (César *et al.*, 2021; Djenontin *et al.*, 2022), there is a noticeable lack of localized studies that evaluate the real-time outcomes of such projects in Rwanda. Much of the existing literature either focuses on generalized African contexts or draws from case studies outside of Rwanda, which limits the contextual relevance of these findings.

Secondly, while the Green Amayaga Project is well-documented in terms of its objectives and implementation strategies through institutional reports and policy briefs, there is limited peer-reviewed research that critically evaluates its tangible contributions to sustainable development in specific sectors such as Kigoma. This creates a disconnect between policy narratives and field-based realities, leaving unanswered questions regarding how the project affects household livelihoods, community participation, and ecological restoration at the grassroots level.

Moreover, there is insufficient scholarly focus on the mediating factors that influence the success of FLR projects, such as land tenure security, governance structures, and community-level technical capacity, within the context of the Green Amayaga Project. While studies have acknowledged these factors in broader terms (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2021; Kassa *et al.*, 2022), their dynamic interplay in Rwanda's socio-political and environmental landscape remains underexplored. Additionally, most research adopts a macro-level evaluation of FLR initiatives, often neglecting the attitudinal and behavioral dimensions of local communities toward environmental conservation. Also, the existing literature highlighted the importance of individual and collective environmental values, yet these insights have not been adequately contextualized within rural Rwandan communities affected by large-scale restoration projects.

Finally, while theoretical frameworks such as the Social-Ecological Systems Theory and Sustainable Livelihoods Framework are increasingly employed in international literature, their application to empirical studies in Rwanda remains sparse. There is a need for theory-driven, context-specific research that bridges the gap between global restoration models and locally grounded sustainability outcomes. This

study aims to address these gaps by focusing on the Green Amayaga Project's implementation in Kigoma Sector, examining both ecological and socio-economic impacts through a localized and participatory lens.

Chapter summary

This chapter explored key concepts such as sustainable development, FLR, and the Green Amayaga Project, guided by relevant theories. It reviews empirical studies on FLR's socio-economic and environmental impacts, identifies key challenges, and presents a conceptual framework. The research gap emphasizes the lack of localized studies in Rwanda, supporting the study's relevance. Building on this foundation, the next chapter presents the methodology used to assess the Green Amayaga Project's impact in Kigoma Sector.

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0. Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology used to examine the Green Amayaga Project's role in promoting sustainable development in Kigoma Sector. It comprises two main sections: the first introduces the project as a case study, including its goals, structure, and significance. The second outlines the research design, including data collection methods and analytical tools. The methodology ensures a systematic and reliable assessment of the project's environmental, social, and economic impacts.

3.1 Presentation of the Case Study: The Green Amayaga Project

The Green Amayaga Project is a six-year initiative officially launched in March 2019 and expected to conclude in March 2025. It is implemented under the National Implementation Modality (NIM) by the Rwanda Environment Management Authority (REMA) in partnership with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF). The project targets four districts in Rwanda's Southern Province: Kamonyi, Ruhango, Nyanza, and Gisagara which together form the Mayaga landscape. The total financing for the project is USD 32,706,365, comprising GEF and UNDP grants, alongside significant co-financing from the Government of Rwanda and other stakeholders.

Figure 3 Map of Mayaga region in Rwanda and land cover of the region.

Source: Agency project document, 2020

The Mayaga region is characterized by low forest cover (approximately 5%) and high pressure on natural resources due to agriculture and population density. Forest degradation has occurred through overharvesting, agricultural encroachment, and erosion. The region's remaining forest patches are rich in biodiversity, hosting unique flora and fauna, and serve as vital carbon and watershed resources.

3.1.1. Vision and Mission

The vision of the Green Amayaga Project is to restore the ecological functionality and biological productivity of the degraded landscapes in the Mayaga region to enhance their capacity to support biodiversity, carbon storage, and resilient rural livelihoods. The mission is to secure biodiversity and carbon benefits while simultaneously strengthening the resilience of livelihoods through forest landscape restoration (FLR) and the adoption of sustainable, clean technologies.

3.1.2. Project Objectives

The Green Amayaga Project aims to achieve three main outcomes:

1. **Development of Forest Restoration Plans:** Establish institutional and legislative frameworks that guide afforestation, biodiversity protection, and land use planning.
2. **Capacity Building:** Strengthen individual and institutional capacities to implement gender-sensitive FLR strategies through knowledge transfer, training, and extension services.
3. **On-the-Ground Implementation:** Apply FLR practices in target areas to protect natural forests, increase productivity of agricultural and plantation forests, and reduce reliance on wood fuel.

Specific measurable targets include:

- Protection of 555 hectares of natural forests, including the Kibirizi-Muyira forest.
- Restoration of 25,000 hectares of degraded lands using sustainable practices.
- Reduction of wood consumption by at least 25% through improved cookstoves and alternative energy solutions.
- Avoidance of 4.7 million tons of CO₂ emissions over five years, and 12.9 million tons over twenty years.
- Development of four FLR plans covering 263,270 hectares.

3.1.3. Target Beneficiaries

The project benefits a wide range of stakeholders, including: Rural households, especially smallholder farmers engaged in agroforestry and sustainable agriculture. Women and youth, through gender-focused capacity building and economic empowerment, Local governments and institutions, via technical and logistical support, and District development platforms such as the Joint Action Development Forum (JADF) which are strengthened for participatory planning.

3.1.4. Project Structure and Governance

The project is governed through a collaborative structure that includes REMA, UNDP, local district governments, and multiple national agencies. It uses the JADF platform to facilitate stakeholder participation and inter-sectoral coordination. Project oversight includes a steering committee and technical working groups. Implementation is decentralized, with district-level plans and institutional frameworks being developed and executed locally.

Three key impact pathways guide the project's activities:

1. Planning and Legal Frameworks: FLR plans integrated with district and sector development frameworks.
2. Capacity Enhancement: Institutional and human resource development through training and participatory tools.
3. FLR Implementation: Afforestation, agroforestry, energy transition, and sustainable land management.

3.1.5. Main project activities

The Green Amayaga Project encompasses a range of integrated activities aimed at restoring degraded landscapes while promoting sustainable livelihoods for local communities. One of its core activities is agroforestry, which involves integrating trees into farming systems to improve soil fertility, enhance biodiversity, and combat erosion. The project has also carried out extensive tree planting and reforestation efforts, particularly in areas that were previously deforested or degraded.

To reduce soil erosion and improve land productivity, the project promotes soil conservation techniques such as terracing, trench digging, and the establishment of radical ditches. In addition, the distribution and use of improved cookstoves have been introduced to reduce pressure on forest resources and improve indoor air quality. As part of its livelihood support initiatives, the project has also provided small livestock, such as goats, pigs and cows to vulnerable households to boost income and food security.

Figure 4: Picture of cookstoves and progressive terraces implemented through the GAM project.

Source: REMA (2021)

Furthermore, the project conducts training workshops and awareness campaigns to educate community members on sustainable land use, environmental protection, and climate change adaptation. These combined efforts not only contribute to environmental restoration but also aim to enhance the socio-economic well-being of the local population. .

In Nyanza District, Which Kigoma Sector belongs, the Green Amayaga Project interventions has been implemented in **7** out of the 10 administrative sectors, specifically those that fall within the Amayaga ecological region. These sectors are Busoro, Kigoma, Ntyazo, Muyira, Kibirizi, Nyagisozi and Busasamana. These sectors were selected due to their vulnerability to environmental degradation, including deforestation, soil erosion, and declining agricultural productivity.

Figure 5: Green Amayaga Project signboard located at Gasoro, Kigali-Huye Road.

Source: Primary data, June, 2025.

The project interventions in these areas have focused on reforestation, agroforestry, soil conservation, and the promotion of sustainable energy technologies. By targeting these 7 sectors, the project aims to restore degraded landscapes, promote sustainable land use, and improve the livelihoods of local communities through environmentally friendly practices. The remaining 3 sectors, which lie outside the Amayaga ecological zone, were not included in the project's scope.

3.1.6. Strategic relevance

The Green Amayaga Project aligns with Rwanda's Vision 2050, the National Strategy for Transformation (NST1), and international environmental goals such as the Bonn Challenge and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Strategically, it plays a critical role in climate mitigation by targeting the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through a combination of forest conservation, afforestation, improved agricultural practices, and energy transition.

One of the project's most significant contributions is the expected avoidance of 4.7 million tons of CO₂ equivalent emissions over a five-year period, with projections reaching 1295 million tons over twenty years. This will be achieved through interventions such as the protection of 555 hectares of natural forests, afforestation of buffer zones and hilltops (approximately 2,000 hectares), and adoption of improved cookstoves and clean energy technologies. Specifically, the dissemination of 60,000 improved cookstoves is expected to drastically reduce reliance on wood fuel, which is currently the primary energy source for over 85% of households in the target districts.

Moreover, the adoption of sustainable land management (SLM) and sustainable forest management (SFM) practices on 25,000 hectares will enhance soil carbon sequestration and reduce emissions from land degradation. The protection and improved management of high biodiversity and carbon stock forests, especially those upgraded to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Category IV status, will further secure long-term carbon storage.

By integrating forest landscape restoration into district land use planning and promoting participatory implementation mechanisms, the project enhances cross-sectoral coordination and builds institutional resilience. This positions the Green Amayaga Project as a scalable model for climate action, ecosystem restoration, and sustainable development in Rwanda and beyond.

3.2. Research design

According to Creswell & Creswell (2017), a research design is “the plan or proposal to conduct research, involving the intersection of philosophy, strategies of inquiry, and specific methods.” It serves as the blueprint for collecting, measuring, and analyzing data in a way that aligns with the research objectives.

For this study, a mixed-methods research design was adopted, specifically a descriptive mixed-methods approach. A mixed-methods design integrates both quantitative and qualitative techniques to explore complex research questions from multiple angles, allowing for the collection of both numerical data and rich narrative information (Plano Clark, 2017). The descriptive nature of the design allows the researcher to systematically describe the characteristics, behaviors, and perceptions of the study population in relation to the Green Amayaga Project's impact on sustainable development. The relevance of a mixed and descriptive design to this study lies in the complex and multi-dimensional nature of the research topic.

The study aims to assess both measurable outcomes (such as changes in household income, environmental practices, and access to energy) and subjective experiences (such as community perceptions of sustainability and project implementation challenges). Quantitative methods through structured questionnaires help capture statistical trends, while qualitative methods, through interviews and observations, provide contextual depth and understanding of local realities. Descriptive research is particularly useful for understanding “what exists” with respect to conditions, attitudes, and trends (Kothari, 2004). In this case, it helps document how the Green Amayaga Project has influenced the social, economic, and environmental well-being of residents in Gahombo Cell. The descriptive mixed-methods design also supports triangulation, which strengthens the validity and reliability of the findings by comparing results from different data sources and techniques (Patton, 2002)

3.3. The Study population

A study population refers to the total group of individuals or units from which the researcher seeks to conclude (Kumar, 2011). It includes all people or entities that meet a set of predefined criteria relevant to the research objectives. According to Polit and Beck (2012), the population in research is “the entire aggregation of cases that meet a designated set of criteria,” and is essential in defining the boundaries of the study. For this particular study, the general population is comprised of all residents of Kigoma Sector, located in Nyanza District, Southern Province of Rwanda. Kigoma Sector is one of the focal areas under the Green Amayaga Project, a large-scale environmental and socio-economic initiative implemented between 2020 and 2024 to restore degraded ecosystems, promote sustainable land use, and improve livelihoods.

According to the National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR, 2022), Kigoma Sector has a population of approximately 41,004 individuals. However, due to the localized nature of the Green Amayaga Project’s activities and the need to focus on an area with intensive project implementation, this study narrows its scope to Gahombo Cell, one of the cells within Kigoma Sector that has been at the core of the project’s interventions. Gahombo Cell was purposefully selected due to its strategic involvement and participation in key project activities, such as afforestation, use of improved cookstoves, soil erosion control measures, and sustainable agriculture practices.

Focusing on Gahombo Cell enabled the researcher to gather detailed and context-specific insights from individuals who have directly experienced the effects of the Green Amayaga Project since its initiation in 2020. This localized focus not only enhances the relevance and accuracy of the findings but also ensures that the respondents possess the required background and firsthand knowledge to assess the project's contribution to sustainable development. Therefore, the study population comprises residents of Gahombo Cell who meet specific eligibility criteria and who represent the broader experience of rural communities engaged in environmental restoration and livelihood enhancement under the Green Amayaga Project framework.

3.3.1 Targeted population

The targeted population, sometimes referred to as the accessible population, is a specific subset of the general population that meets certain characteristics relevant to the research objectives and from which the actual sample is drawn. According to (Bryman, 2016) the target population consists of the individuals or groups about whom the researcher intends to make inferences. It should be clearly defined to ensure relevance, focus, and reliability in data collection.

In this study, the targeted population includes individual residents of Gahombo Cell within Kigoma Sector who are direct beneficiaries of the Green Amayaga Project. These beneficiaries are people who have actively participated in at least one of the project's intervention components. These components include:

- Tree planting and reforestation activities
- Adoption of improved cookstoves
- Soil erosion control practices
- Agroforestry
- Sustainable land management techniques

These individuals were selected as the primary focus of the study because they have firsthand knowledge and experience with the project's activities and impacts. They are therefore best positioned to provide accurate reflections on how the Green Amayaga Project has influenced environmental restoration, economic well-being, and sustainable practices in their community. The choice to focus on direct beneficiaries ensures that the study collects informed, experience-based responses, which are essential for evaluating the effectiveness and sustainability of project interventions.

Furthermore, this approach aligns with the principle of participant relevance in research, which emphasizes engaging individuals who are both knowledgeable about and affected by the phenomenon under investigation (Williams, 2022). By narrowing the scope to this defined group within Birembo Village of Gahombo Cell, the study ensures clarity, focus, and depth of analysis, while also providing grounded insights that can inform future environmental and development policies at the sector or district level.

3.5. Sampling Method

Sampling is the process of selecting a subset of individuals from a population to represent the entire group. It is a critical step in ensuring that the data collected is both manageable and representative. According to Teddlie and Yu (2007), sampling methods in mixed-methods research should allow for both the generalizability of quantitative data and the depth of qualitative insights. This study employed a combination of a purposive sampling technique, commonly used in mixed-methods research designs.

3.5.1. Purposive sampling

According to Palinkas *et al.* (2015), purposive sampling is useful in identifying information-rich cases that offer deep insights into the research phenomenon. In this study, purposive sampling, also called judgmental sampling, was applied to select individuals from Birembo Village who were known to be direct beneficiaries of the Green Amayaga Project. This technique allowed the researcher to deliberately select participants based on predefined criteria such as project participation, residence duration, and knowledge of local environmental changes.

3.5.2. Sample size determination and selection of respondents

To determine the appropriate sample size, the study used Yamane's formula (Yamane, 1967), which provides a simplified method for calculating sample size from a given population size when the confidence level and margin of error are known. The formula is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = Sample size
- N = Total population
- e = Desired margin of error (set at 0.05 for 95% confidence level)

According to local administrative records, Birembo village has an estimated population of 152 residents. Substituting into the formula:

$$n = \frac{152}{1 + 152(0.05)^2} = \frac{152}{1 + 3} = 111.$$

The obtained sample size was further narrowed so that the researcher can get accurate and reliable data. This involved the selection of respondents. Respondent selection is a critical step in any research process, especially when evaluating community-based projects like the Green Amayaga Project. According to Patton (2015), careful selection of participants ensures that the data collected is both relevant and credible, particularly when the research seeks to assess lived experiences and project outcomes from the perspective of beneficiaries. In this study, the respondents were selected based on a well-defined set of eligibility criteria to ensure that only knowledgeable and directly affected individuals were included in the sample. These criteria were established to enhance the validity and reliability of the data, given the study's focus on evaluating the impact of the Green Amayaga Project on sustainable development in Gahombo Cell.

3.5.2. Eligibility criteria for respondents

To qualify as a respondent, individuals had to meet all the following conditions:

1. **Direct beneficiary of the Green Amayaga Project:** Only individuals who had actively participated in at least one intervention, such as tree planting, agroforestry, improved cookstove adoption, or soil conservation, were selected. This ensured the respondents had experiential knowledge of the project's objectives and outcomes.
2. **Resident of Gahombo Cell, Birembo Village since before 2020:** To allow for meaningful comparisons of environmental and livelihood conditions before and after the project's implementation, participants had to have lived in Birembo Cell for at least three years prior to 2020. This aligns with the recommendation by Babbie (2020) that longitudinal familiarity enhances the depth of data in impact evaluations.

3. **Aged 18 years or older:** To comply with ethical standards for informed consent, only adults (18+) were included. Adults were considered more capable of offering reflective and responsible insights about long-term environmental and socio-economic changes.
4. **Willing and able to participate voluntarily:** Informed and voluntary participation was a key requirement, in line with ethical research principles outlined by the American Psychological Association (APA, 2017). All participants were required to express their consent and were free to decline or withdraw without any consequence.

After applying these criteria, 97 population out of 111 meet these criteria. Therefore, a survey was done for 97 people.

These selection criteria ensured that the study captured reliable, firsthand perspectives on the Green Amayaga Project's contributions to sustainability. It also ensured that participants were in the best position to provide comparative reflections based on observable changes over time, enhancing both the accuracy and contextual richness of the study findings.

3.6. Data collection instruments and techniques

This research needs both primary and secondary data. The primary data were obtained using a questionnaire survey and field observation from the targeted population beneficiaries, Local leaders in Kigoma Sector. Secondary data were sourced from written books and reports, electronic sources, historical archives, annual reports, and other documents of Kigoma Sector. Data collection is a foundational phase in research, involving the selection of tools and procedures that best suit the research design and objectives. According to Creswell (2014), the choice of data collection instruments in a mixed-methods study should aim to gather both numeric trends and in-depth perspectives to enable comprehensive analysis. To explore the contribution of the Green Amayaga Project to sustainable development in Kigoma Sector, this study employed a triangulated data collection approach, using three main instruments: structured questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and field observations.

3.6.1. Survey questionnaire

Structured questionnaires were used as the primary tool for collecting quantitative data. These questionnaires were designed to capture information on variables such as: Household income levels,

access to renewable energy (e.g., improved cookstoves), land productivity and agricultural practices, environmental awareness, and behaviors. The questionnaires included a mix of closed-ended questions for ease of analysis and open-ended questions to allow respondents to elaborate on key issues. The digital tool KoboToolbox was used to administer the questionnaires. KoboToolbox (created through <https://kobotoolbox.org>) is widely recognized for its suitability in field-based data collection, especially in rural areas where offline access may be needed. The survey tool can be accessed here <https://ee.kobotoolbox.org/i/G0qaXVyE>.

3.6.2. Interviews

To complement the quantitative data and gain deeper insights into community experiences and perceptions, semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected residents and local leaders. Interview participants were chosen based on their involvement or knowledge of the Green Amayaga Project's implementation. These interviews followed a flexible guide, allowing the researcher to probe for additional details while maintaining thematic consistency. The key themes explored included: perceived environmental changes since project implementation, community involvement and participation in the project, benefits and challenges experienced during the project rollout, and suggestions for future improvement of environmental initiatives. Semi-structured interviews are particularly valuable for understanding how individuals interpret and give meaning to their experiences (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). They provided rich, narrative data that supported the interpretation of quantitative trends.

In addition to face-to-face data collection methods, the researcher employed telephone calls to reach beneficiaries who were not available on the scheduled data collection days. This approach helped ensure inclusivity and improved the response rate by allowing remote data collection. Telephone interviews were also conducted with village leaders and sector chiefs who supervised and monitored the tree planting activities under the Green Amayaga Project. These key informants provided valuable insights and verified information related to the project implementation and impact at the community level.

3.6.4. Field observations

Direct field observations were also carried out to verify project-related developments in the study area physically. These included: the presence and condition of planted trees, the use and installation of improved cookstoves, evidence of soil erosion control structures (e.g., terraces, trenches, or contours),

and General environmental and land-use changes. An observational checklist guided the process to ensure consistency and objectivity in documenting findings. Observations allowed the researcher to confirm the existence and functionality of physical project outputs, thereby strengthening the reliability of self-reported data.

3.7. Data analysis procedures

Data analysis is a vital stage in the research process where raw data are organized, interpreted, and transformed into meaningful information. As noted by Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014), data analysis involves identifying patterns, relationships, and insights that respond to the research objectives. Given the study's mixed-methods approach, both quantitative and qualitative data analysis techniques were employed to ensure a comprehensive and balanced interpretation of findings.

3.7.1. Quantitative data analysis

Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize and describe the basic features of the data, including:

- Frequencies and percentages to show the distribution of responses across key variables (e.g., access to improved cookstoves, awareness of tree planting programs).
- Means and standard deviations to understand central tendencies and variations in variables such as household income and land productivity.
- Data visualizations such as tables, bar charts, and pie charts were generated to enhance clarity and interpretation of results.

These quantitative techniques helped identify general trends and patterns across the sample population, which were then compared with qualitative insights for deeper understanding.

3.7.2. Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative data from semi-structured interviews and field observations were analyzed using a thematic analysis approach, following the framework outlined by Braun and Clarke (2019). The process involved the following steps:

1. **Transcription and Familiarization:** Interview recordings were transcribed, and observation notes were reviewed to become immersed in the data.

2. **Coding:** Key phrases and ideas were labeled with codes representing relevant themes such as “community participation,” “environmental changes,” and “project challenges.”
3. **Theme Development:** Similar codes were grouped into broader categories and themes, allowing the researcher to detect recurring patterns in the narratives.
4. **Interpretation:** Themes were interpreted in light of the study objectives and compared with quantitative findings for consistency and explanation.

This thematic approach enabled the researcher to extract rich, contextualized meanings from the participants’ lived experiences, adding depth and nuance to the quantitative trends.

3.8. Ethical consideration

This study was conducted in strict adherence to ethical research principles to ensure the dignity, rights, and welfare of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from each respondent after clearly explaining the purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature of their involvement. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents retained the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed by excluding personal identifiers from the dataset and securely storing digital data using encrypted tools such as KoboToolbox. Special consideration was given to elderly participants to ensure respectful engagement, and the researcher obtained ethical clearance in the form of a recommendation letter from the University of Rwanda.

3.9 Limitations of the Study

This study was limited to Kigoma Sector and may not comprehensively reflect the experiences of beneficiaries in other sectors covered by the Green Amayaga Project. The research relied on self-reported data from surveys and interviews, which may be influenced by social desirability or recall bias. Additionally, some respondents lacked detailed knowledge about certain technical components of the project, which may have limited the accuracy or depth of their responses. Religious and cultural beliefs particularly among groups like the Abakusi, also affected participation in specific interventions such as cookstove usage. Despite these limitations, the study provides meaningful insights into the project’s role in promoting sustainable development at the community level.

Chapter summary

This chapter presented the methodology employed to assess the contribution of the Green Amayaga Project to sustainable development in Gahombo Cell, Kigoma Sector. The study adopted a mixed-methods descriptive design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to gather comprehensive and reliable data. The target population consisted of residents who directly benefited from the project, and a sample size of 152 respondents was determined using Yamane's formula. A combination of purposive and random sampling techniques ensured the selection of informed and representative participants. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and field observations, while both SPSS-based statistical analysis and thematic analysis were used to interpret the data. The chapter also addressed limitations such as geographic scope and recall bias and discussed the ethical measures taken to ensure confidentiality, informed consent, and academic integrity. The next chapter presents and discusses the key findings derived from the data collected, offering insights into how the Green Amayaga Project has influenced environmental conservation and socio-economic development in the study area.

CHAPTER IV: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.0. Introduction

This chapter presents and discusses the findings of the study on the Green Amayaga Project and Sustainable Development in Kigoma Sector, specifically in Birembo village, Gahombo cell. The findings are based on both quantitative and qualitative data, gathered through a combination of methods to ensure a comprehensive analysis. Quantitative data were obtained through a survey questionnaire administered to 97 project beneficiaries residing in Birembo village. This instrument was designed to collect measurable inputs regarding the project's impact on the livelihoods and environment of the community.

In addition, qualitative data were collected through three key informant interviews: one with the Agricultural Officer of Kigoma Sector, another with the Green Amayaga Project Manager, and one with the village leader, who also coordinated the teams responsible for tree planting and trench construction. The researcher also conducted four in-depth interviews with selected community members to capture detailed personal experiences, opinions, and insights. Furthermore, field observations were made within Birembo village to visually assess the tangible outputs of the project, including planted trees, trenches, and other visible interventions related to land restoration and environmental protection.

4.1. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Understanding the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents is essential in evaluating the relevance, inclusiveness, and potential sustainability of the Green Amayaga Project interventions. This section provides an overview of key demographic variables, including gender, age, marital status, level of education, and main livelihood activities. These factors influence how individuals participate in and benefit from environmental and livelihood-oriented development projects.

Table 1: The Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	59	60.8%
	Female	38	39.2%
Age Group	18-35 years	19	19.6%
	36-52 years	54	55.7%
	53 years and above	24	24.7%
Marital Status	Married	73	75.3%

	Single	12	12.4%
	Widowed	10	10.3%
	Separated/Divorced	2	2.1%
Main Livelihood Activity	Crop Farming	72	74.2%
	Livestock Farming	72	74.2%
	Paid Employment	48	49.5%
	Trading	19	19.6%
	Students	7	7.2%
Level of Education	No Formal Education	24	24.7%
	Primary Education	47	48.5%
	Secondary Education	38	39.2%
	Vocational Training	16	16.5%
	Tertiary Education	6	6.2%

Source: Primary data June, 2025

The socio-demographic data presented above offer critical insight into the composition of the respondents and the broader community dynamics that shape the outcomes of the Green Amayaga Project. Out of 97 respondents, 60.8% were male and 39.2% were female. This moderate gender imbalance could be explained by cultural or logistical factors in rural settings, where men are more likely to participate in public surveys or be present at home during working hours. Nevertheless, the participation of both genders indicates that the Green Amayaga Project has reached a broad cross-section of the community.

The age distribution shows that a majority (55.7%) of the respondents fall within the 36–52 years’ age group, which is considered the peak productive age. This implies that the project is engaging adults who are actively involved in land use, farming, and environmental activities. Another 24.7% are aged 53 years and above, reflecting the participation of elder residents, many of whom may hold traditional knowledge and authority in land stewardship. The 18–35 age group, representing 19.6%, includes youth whose involvement is essential for the long-term sustainability of conservation and agricultural practices introduced by the project.

As seen from the table, a significant 75.3% of respondents were married, indicating that the majority of respondents come from stable family units. This is crucial in rural development as married couples often share responsibilities in farming and household decision-making. Lower proportions were single (12.4%), widowed (10.3%), and separated/divorced (2.1%), showing a variety of household types that may influence the level of participation or benefit from the project.

According to Martin *et al.* (2016), integrated crop–livestock systems are foundational to sustainable agriculture because they promote ecological and resource-use synergies. In such systems, livestock manure enhances soil fertility for crops, while crop residues and by-products serve as feed for animals. This dynamic leads to a more closed-loop, resilient farming system that reduces dependency on external inputs and promotes long-term environmental health. This is reflected in the data, 72 respondents (74.2%) reported engaging in crop farming, and the same number (72 respondents or 74.2%) also practiced livestock farming. This equal representation is not accidental but rather reflects the integrated nature of rural livelihoods in areas like Birembo village, where crop–livestock farming systems function as a unified strategy rather than separate economic activities.

This integration enhances ecosystem services such as soil fertility, erosion control, and biological regulation. Specifically, synergy between crops and livestock—common at the local level—supports nutrient cycling and sustainable land use practices, which are essential for landscape-level sustainability. In Birembo village, these practices are evident through the Green Amayaga Project’s interventions, which promote soil conservation techniques and agroforestry approaches that inherently link crop and animal farming. This integrated approach also has economic and social advantages, including increased resilience to market or climate shocks, improved food security, and shared knowledge among farmers. By that, one can say that crop farmers are also livestock keepers, or those who keep livestock are also crop farmers. Both are reasonable in rural settings. Therefore, the presence of both crop and livestock farming among nearly three-quarters of respondents is not only typical of rural livelihoods in Rwanda but also aligns with global best practices in sustainable agriculture.

In addition, 49.5% reported engaging in paid employment, including casual labor, salaried jobs, and motorbike transport (moto-taxi). These findings suggest a growing trend in income diversification, which enhances household resilience. 19.6% were involved in trading, while 7.2% were students, a lower number attributed to school hours during data collection. Most respondents had primary (48.5%) or secondary (39.2%) education, reflecting widespread access to basic education. However, 24.7% had no formal education, which may limit their ability to interpret technical agricultural or environmental instructions unless supported with visual or oral training methods. Notably, 16.5% had attended vocational training centers (VTCs) or former SERAI, equipping them with practical skills that align well with project activities.

However, only 6.2% of the respondents had completed tertiary education, which points to limited access to higher learning opportunities in the area. This low percentage may be attributed to multiple factors. First, in rural settings like Birembo, many individuals consider completion of secondary education sufficient, especially when they can engage in agriculture or informal employment soon after graduation. Second, the timing of the survey conducted during working hours on weekdays may have coincided with the absence of students currently enrolled in universities, who were likely attending classes or exams in distant urban centers.

Additionally, some individuals with tertiary qualifications may have migrated to other regions in search of employment, a common trend in rural Rwanda. This educational profile has implications for the implementation of development projects such as Green Amayaga. While basic literacy levels are fairly high, the limited presence of highly educated individuals might challenge the community's capacity to fully engage with technical training, record keeping, or formalized project planning unless complemented by capacity-building initiatives.

4.2. Participation in project interventions

The Green Amayaga Project implemented a range of interventions aimed at promoting sustainable land use and improving rural livelihoods in Kigoma Sector. Based on survey responses (n=97), a large portion of beneficiaries reported participating in one or more project activities (see Figure 6).

As shown in Figure 6, the most widely adopted activity was improved cookstoves, with approximately 77.32% (75 respondents) indicating active participation. This high participation is explained by the project's strategy to distribute cookstoves across the entire community, ensuring that nearly every household received one. The aim was to reduce reliance on wood fuel, thereby decreasing deforestation and indoor air pollution. This aligns with the Green Amayaga Project's goal to cut wood consumption by 25% and reduce CO₂ emissions, as outlined in the project's environmental strategy (UNDP, 2020).

Following this, tree planting was reported by 65.98% (64 respondents), while agroforestry and soil conservation activities (notably trench digging and terracing) were each cited by 56.70% (55 respondents).

Figure 6: Participation in the Green Amayaga Project interventions

Source: Primary data, June 2025.

These three interventions are essential components of the Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) framework, intended to improve ecosystem resilience, enhance soil fertility, and restore degraded lands. As noted in Chapter 2, such activities also contribute to long-term food security and income diversification, especially when implemented with sufficient technical support and local participation (Moluh Njoya *et al.*, 2025; César *et al.*, 2021). Goat distribution was cited by 29.90% (29 respondents). Unlike the universally distributed stoves, goats were awarded as performance-based incentives to individuals who demonstrated commitment in tree care and contour/trench maintenance. This targeted approach aimed to both reward engagement and stimulate long-term behavioral change in environmental stewardship, consistent with the Environmental Stewardship Theory discussed in your theoretical framework (Bennett *et al.*, 2021a).

Training and workshop participation was reported by only 15.46% (15 respondents), making it the least participated intervention. On the surface, this may suggest limited investment in capacity building. However, further context reveals that community members were invited to mobilization meetings at the start of the project, during which they were informed about the project’s goals, what was expected of them

(primarily the provision of land for tree planting and terracing), and the project’s non-compensation policy regarding land expropriation.

These meetings were organized through community gatherings and football events, accompanied by the slogan "*Green Amayaga*" to which residents responded "*Amayaga Atoshye*" (loosely translated as “Mayaga is flourishing”). Despite the participatory and informative nature of these meetings, most respondents did not consider them as training or workshops, viewing them instead as public mobilization events. This explains the low self-reported participation rate in formal capacity-building sessions.

Nonetheless, in the researcher’s view, these meetings served a training function by transferring key knowledge about environmental practices, the importance of tree care, and the rationale behind terrace digging. This is consistent with the broader understanding of informal learning in community-based projects, where training is not limited to classroom settings but also includes participatory awareness and demonstration sessions (Chazdon et al., 2020; Bennett et al., 2021a). Therefore, the apparent low participation in "training" reflects a perception gap rather than an actual lack of knowledge dissemination.

4.3. Socio-economic benefits of the Green Amayaga Project

This section addresses the first specific objective of the study was to examine the socio-economic benefits of the Green Amayaga Project to local communities in Kigoma Sector. Survey data, along with in-depth interviews with project beneficiaries and key stakeholders, revealed a range of interconnected benefits that spanned household income, food security, time management, and agricultural productivity.

Figure 7: Socio-economic benefits of the Green Amayaga Project

Source: Primary data, June, 2025.

4.3.1 Energy access and household efficiency

One of the cornerstone interventions of the Green Amayaga Project was the universal distribution of improved cookstoves, commonly known as Rondereza, to all participating households. This initiative was not only among the most visible but also among the most immediately impactful in terms of household welfare and environmental conservation.

The project's focus on clean energy solutions was directly informed by the environmental context of the Amayaga region, historically one of the most ecologically degraded areas in Rwanda. As highlighted in the background of this study, the region had suffered extensive deforestation, soil erosion, and land degradation, largely driven by overdependence on firewood as a primary energy source. In areas like Kigoma Sector, the daily demand for fuelwood led to the destruction of native tree cover, stripping hillsides of vegetation, and worsening land vulnerability.

In response to this degradation, the Green Amayaga Project prioritized the promotion of sustainable household energy practices. The Rondereza cookstoves were designed to significantly reduce firewood consumption by up to 60% in some cases, thus addressing one of the root causes of environmental decline in the region. Unlike traditional three-stone fires, the improved stoves concentrate heat, retain smoke, and require smaller pieces of wood to function efficiently. This technological adaptation not only benefited the environment but also transformed daily domestic life.

From a household perspective, the benefits were multifaceted. Survey results revealed that 79.38% identified cleaner energy access as a major benefit. Interviews further underscored the practical changes the cookstoves introduced. One female beneficiary shared: *"With dry firewood, it cooks well and quickly. We no longer need to go far into the bush to collect wood."* This shift has greatly reduced the time and physical burden, particularly for women and children, who traditionally bear the responsibility of fuel collection. By saving hours previously spent searching for firewood, beneficiaries now have more time to invest in farming, childcare, education, or income-generating activities. This has not only improved time efficiency but also had ripple effects on overall household productivity and well-being.

Furthermore, the cookstoves have contributed to improved household health by reducing exposure to indoor smoke, which is known to cause respiratory infections, particularly among women and children. Cleaner indoor air has thus become an unanticipated health co-benefit of the project's energy intervention.

The environmental gains have also been significant. With reduced reliance on tree cutting, the project helped relieve pressure on the few remaining forest patches in the Amayaga landscape. Interestingly, many respondents reported that the small amount of wood they still use now often comes from tree pruning activities a practice encouraged by the project to maintain planted trees while sourcing sustainable fuel.

Thus, the cookstove initiative simultaneously addressed three intertwined challenges: environmental degradation, gendered labor burdens, and energy poverty. Its effectiveness demonstrates how small-scale, locally appropriate technologies can play a transformative role in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action). By reducing both the demand for unsustainable firewood harvesting and the daily burdens of rural households, the cookstove component of the Green Amayaga Project serves as a practical example of integrated, people-centered development.

4.3.2. Income generation and financial savings

The Green Amayaga Project contributed substantially to improved household income and financial stability among local beneficiaries. Based on the data, 73 out of 97 respondents (75.26%) reported an increase in household income as a direct or indirect outcome of participating in the project. This income growth was attributed to a combination of employment opportunities, reduced household expenses, and increased agricultural productivity.

One of the primary drivers of income generation was employment during the project's implementation phase, particularly in activities such as trench digging, tree planting, and terrace construction. According to both survey respondents and key informants, many community members, especially the youth, were engaged in manual labor and were paid approximately RWF 1,200 per day. While this rate may appear modest, it represented a significant financial opportunity in a rural context where employment is often seasonal or informal. This income provided families with the means to cover essential needs such as food, clothing, and small household investments. As one local leader affirmed during the interviews: *“People got jobs digging terraces and planting trees and were paid. It helped them feed their families.”*

In addition to direct employment, the project led to a noticeable reduction in household expenditures, especially on energy. The distribution of improved cookstoves (locally referred to as Rondereza) allowed households to use less firewood, thereby reducing the frequency and cost of fuel collection or

purchase. Many respondents explained that much of the firewood they now use comes from pruned branches of the very trees they planted, making energy access not only more affordable but also more sustainable. This shift in energy consumption patterns contributed to savings that could be redirected toward other priorities.

Another key contributor to financial improvement was enhanced agricultural output. Through soil conservation measures like terracing, as well as improved manure retention and runoff control, farmers reported better yields of staple crops such as maize, soybeans, and beans. Some even began harvesting fruit from planted agroforestry trees, such as avocado and mango, which added nutritional and commercial value. The increase in surplus produce allowed households to engage in small-scale selling of crops at local markets, providing an additional income stream beyond subsistence farming.

A critical outcome of increased income and savings was its effect on educational access. About 27 respondents (27.84%) reported being able to pay school fees for their children, a goal that had previously been challenging due to financial hardship. Some families also reported improvements in children's school attendance and retention, suggesting a broader social benefit linked to financial empowerment. For many, the ability to support education was not just a practical achievement but a source of pride and dignity, marking a shift toward greater household resilience.

4.3.3. Improved agricultural productivity

“Now, the water channels catch runoff and prevent erosion. Our soybeans grow better, and we’ve even started harvesting avocados,” shared an agricultural advisor involved in the Green Amayaga Project. This testimony vividly illustrates the direct impact of landscape restoration on agricultural productivity and food security at the household level. Through simple but transformative environmental interventions such as water channeling, soil retention, and agroforestry, farmers in the project area are experiencing improved crop yields and diversification of produce.

According to Chazdon *et al.* (2021), FLR initiatives improve soil fertility, regulate water cycles, and create microclimates conducive to crop growth. Field findings from this study strongly support these scholarly insights. A total of 70 respondents, representing 72.16% of the surveyed households, reported improved farming productivity as a result of Green Amayaga interventions. This was largely attributed to a combination of agroforestry practices, soil conservation techniques such as terracing and trenching, and

better land management strategies. The terraces and trenches helped to slow water runoff, reduce erosion, and retain critical soil nutrients. In parallel, the introduction of trees contributed to the stabilization of slopes, enhancement of soil organic matter, and the improvement of local microclimates—factors that are essential for sustainable agriculture. Moreover, the reduction in erosion led to greater manure retention, which had a direct and positive influence on crop yields.

4.3.4. Nutrition, food security, and access to education

The Green Amayaga Project has significantly improved the livelihoods of beneficiary households in Kigoma Sector by enhancing food security, reducing labor burdens, and enabling access to education. These interconnected gains emerged as secondary benefits of the project’s core interventions in agroforestry, sustainable land management, and energy efficiency.

According to the survey results, 65 out of 97 respondents (67.01%) reported better access to food and improved nutrition. This was directly linked to increases in agricultural productivity, a result of the introduction of terracing, tree planting, and soil conservation practices. The project’s agroforestry approach helped restore soil fertility, reduced erosion, and supported higher crop yields, particularly for beans, maize, and other staples. The planting of fruit-bearing trees such as avocado and mango further contributed to dietary diversity, improving household nutrition while also providing additional sources of income.

Interviewees confirmed these improvements. A farmer in Birembo village remarked: *“Before, water would wash everything downhill. Now the terraces keep soil and manure in place, and our crops do much better. We can eat and sell what we produce.”* In addition to enhancing nutrition, the project brought about a major transformation in household time use, especially through the distribution of improved cookstoves (Rondereza). These stoves consume significantly less firewood and cook food faster than traditional three-stone fires. This shift allowed beneficiaries—particularly women and children—to save time previously spent collecting wood or tending long cooking fires.

Time once consumed by survival tasks could now be redirected to productive or restorative activities, such as farming, attending school, or simply resting. One female respondent illustrated this change: *“It used to take us hours to collect wood and cook food. Now we finish early and have more time for other things.”* The ripple effect of time savings and better food access led to improved household resilience. With more

stable sources of food and reduced dependency on external inputs, families could make forward-looking decisions, including investments in education. According to the survey, 27 out of 97 respondents (27.84%) reported that they were now able to pay school fees for their children, a benefit made possible through project-generated income and savings from reduced firewood use.

For many families, this marked the first time they had consistent means to support their children's education. Interview data revealed that this shift was deeply meaningful, not only for the students but also for the parents who viewed education as a pathway out of poverty. In some cases, children who had dropped out due to financial hardship were re-enrolled in school, thanks to improved household income and budgeting flexibility. These results reflect the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, which identifies time, health, education, and asset accumulation as essential components of long-term development. By improving land productivity, reducing daily labor burdens, and creating financial flexibility, the Green Amayaga Project strengthened the structural foundations upon which households can build secure and self-sufficient lives.

However, disparities remain. Interviews revealed that households in areas with limited project coverage or minimal follow-up support continued to face food insecurity and could not consistently afford school fees. In some villages, beneficiaries noted that tree planting or trench digging had not reached their farms, limiting their ability to benefit from improved harvests or reduced fuelwood demand. These gaps underscore the need for more inclusive implementation in future phases of the project.

4.3.6 Soil erosion control

Soil erosion control is one of the key environmental goals of the Green Amayaga Project. Based on the data, 59.79% acknowledged a noticeable reduction in soil erosion as a result of project interventions such as terracing and tree planting. However, this proportion remains lower than other perceived benefits such as cleaner energy and household income, suggesting that erosion control has not been uniformly achieved across all areas.

One of the primary reasons for this lower percentage is that many of the trees planted through the project are still young and have not yet developed the deep root systems necessary to stabilize soil effectively. During interviews, local agronomists emphasized that while the trees were distributed with clear instructions, their soil-conserving potential would only be realized fully over time. Respondents were

advised that, in the long term, the trees would help retain soil, prevent landslides, and contribute to ecosystem recovery, but patience was needed until they reached maturity.

Another issue affecting erosion control is the maintenance of the anti-erosion trenches. Although the initial digging of trenches was successful in many areas, field observations revealed that some trenches were not well maintained. In several places, runoff water had filled the trenches with debris and silt, reducing their effectiveness. Poor upkeep has allowed overflow, which continues to cause soil displacement, especially during the rainy season. Additionally, the presence of livestock, often tied near trenches or young trees, has compromised the stability of the soil and reduced the sustainability of the interventions.

Geographical coverage also played a role in limiting the effectiveness of erosion control. While the project was active in many villages, certain areas within Gahombo Cell were not included in the implementation. As confirmed by the sector agronomist, these areas were not prioritized due to resource constraints or logistical challenges. This exclusion means that runoff from untreated slopes in these neighboring locations can still affect soil quality and agricultural fields in the broader sector, including areas where the project was fully implemented.

Furthermore, while the project mobilized the community through public meetings and awareness campaigns, some residents still lack a strong sense of responsibility for maintaining terraces or protecting trees. Field visits revealed instances where trenches were deliberately removed during cultivation or trees were damaged due to negligence. Without continuous administrative enforcement and follow-up, the impact of erosion control efforts may remain inconsistent across the sector.

4.4. Attitudes towards environmental conservation.

One of the Green Amayaga Project's most profound impacts was the transformation in local attitudes towards environmental conservation. From the outset, the project aimed not only to restore degraded landscapes but also to cultivate a culture of environmental stewardship among rural communities. In Kigoma Sector, this shift is evident both in the numbers and in the reflections shared by beneficiaries. According to survey responses, 76 reported that their attitude toward environmental conservation "increased greatly," while another 22 noted a "slight increase" in awareness and commitment. Only two respondents claimed no change at all. These figures suggest that over 95% of beneficiaries experienced a positive shift in their environmental attitudes after participating in the project.

Figure 8: Shift in attitudes toward environmental conservation

Source: Primary data, June 2025

Several respondents expressed that the Green Amayaga Project opened their eyes to the risks of deforestation, the value of soil protection, and the long-term importance of sustaining the land for future generations. One participant shared: *“In recent years, I didn't protect our environment, but now I'm the first who knows the reasons for protecting our environment.”* Another noted: *“The project taught me that it's not just the government's job to protect the environment—it starts with us.”* Others connected conservation directly with their livelihood: *“Because I now understand how our actions affect the land and future generations. If I take care of the land, it will keep feeding my family.”*

This attitudinal shift is reflected in the specific environmental practices now commonly adopted. For example, 79 respondents reported that they actively plant and protect trees, 72 use improved cookstoves to reduce wood consumption, and 68 now avoid deforestation or bush burning. Furthermore, 67 engage in managing soil erosion and runoff, while 58 said they are now teaching others about environmental care. When asked directly whether they now feel personally responsible for protecting the environment, a remarkable 96.3% said yes. Their reasons reveal a deep, personal transformation.

These reflections align with existing literature, such as Deville *et al.* (2021), which confirms that direct engagement with nature increases pro-environmental behavior. Similarly, IHEMEZIE *et al.* (2021) emphasize that personal values and lived experiences strongly influence conservation attitudes. These

findings are consistent with the transformative effect witnessed in Kigoma, where hands-on involvement in terracing, tree planting, and erosion control has shifted conservation from an abstract concept to a personal responsibility. It is also important to note the role of community-based learning and exposure.

Though many respondents stated that they never attended formal training sessions, public mobilizations, slogan campaigns, and communal activities such as tree planting and football tournaments all served as informal environmental education. This was confirmed by local leaders and echoed by several respondents who said they learned by doing, or by observing changes in their land. Even those who initially lacked interest or doubted the project's relevance later acknowledged their changed perspectives after witnessing visible improvements in vegetation, water retention, and household productivity.

4.5 Green Amayaga Project implementation challenges

Despite the Green Amayaga Project's visible achievements in promoting sustainability and restoring degraded landscapes, several challenges emerged during its implementation in Kigoma Sector. These challenges affected both the effectiveness and the equity of project outcomes, and they provide valuable lessons for future environmental development programs.

4.5.1 Limited and unequal distribution of project benefits

One of the most reported challenges from beneficiaries was the inequitable distribution of inputs, including cookstoves, goats, fruit trees, and agroforestry seedlings. Though the project aimed for inclusivity, some respondents claimed that only certain individuals—often connected to local leaders—received full benefits, while others were left out despite registering. Several responses mentioned favoritism, nepotism, and even corruption in the allocation of project resources. *“Some leaders who were supposed to distribute the things from the project gave them to their relatives,”* one respondent claimed. This uneven distribution generated frustration and discouraged community participation in some areas. Moreover, people who felt excluded were less likely to maintain terraces or protect the trees, potentially undermining long-term sustainability.

4.5.2 Insufficient training and awareness

Although the project emphasized environmental conservation, formal training sessions were limited, particularly in the early phases. Respondents noted that while there were mobilization efforts through slogans and football matches, these were not viewed as technical training. As a result, some participants misunderstood how to properly maintain trenches, apply manure to young trees, or use cookstoves efficiently. Interview insights confirmed this issue. One farmer noted that he did not receive training on tree planting, and his seedlings died due to poor planting and lack of care. Others expressed confusion about the project's overall goals, fearing at first that it involved land expropriation.

4.5.3 Incomplete geographic coverage

Another major issue was that not all villages in Kigoma Sector were covered by the project, creating disparities in impact and outcomes. For example, areas like Kingina, Rugarama, were not included in tree planting or trenching activities, even though they are located near erosion-prone zones. Residents in these areas expressed concern that erosion and runoff from untreated hillsides could still affect their plots, even if they had participated in project activities themselves. *“If they don’t treat the upper villages, the water will still reach us. It’s not enough to stop it in just one place,”* said one resident.

4.5.3. Community perceptions, beliefs, and mindset barriers

While the Green Amayaga Project was generally welcomed by the community, particularly for its interventions in tree planting, trenching, and agroforestry, it initially faced resistance regarding the adoption of improved cookstoves, especially from a religious group known as the Abakusi. This resistance was not directed at the entire project, but rather at the cookstove component, which became the target of misinformation and religious suspicion.

According to field interviews, members of the Abakusi sect were reluctant to receive and use the cookstoves. Their hesitation was driven by conspiratorial beliefs that gained traction during the COVID-19 pandemic, a period marked by global uncertainty and widespread rumor-mongering. One persistent rumor claimed that cookstoves contained microchips that would be used to control or track people, allegedly as part of a hidden agenda linked to COVID-19. In an extreme case, a community member

reportedly broke open the stove to check if there was a chip inside, revealing the depth of distrust and anxiety surrounding the intervention.

“He thought the stove had a chip that would control people. He broke it open to see inside,” a Sector Agronomist recounted during interviews. This belief, though unfounded, was reinforced by fear, lack of information, and the broader social climate of the pandemic, which limited the effectiveness of early mobilization campaigns. Public gatherings were discouraged due to social distancing measures, reducing the project’s ability to hold in-person meetings and live demonstrations where such misinformation could have been dispelled.

Importantly, the Abakusi group did accept other interventions of the project—such as tree planting and trenching—suggesting that their resistance was not ideological opposition to environmental conservation, but rather a technology-specific fear driven by a combination of religious belief and pandemic-related paranoia. This experience highlights how certain innovations, especially those that involve unfamiliar technologies, can become flashpoints for deeper societal anxieties if not adequately explained and contextualized.

Over time, this resistance began to soften as more households successfully used the stoves without harm and community leaders clarified the intent of the intervention. However, the initial reluctance affected stove adoption rates and may have delayed full realization of the project’s clean energy goals. This experience illustrates the importance of preemptively addressing cultural and religious concerns when introducing unfamiliar technologies. It also shows that in times of crisis—like the COVID-19 pandemic—projects must be prepared to combat misinformation not only through formal training but also through trust-based communication, including the involvement of respected community figures, religious leaders, and early adopters who can help dispel fear and build confidence.

4.6. Hypothesis verification

This section assesses the validity of the three specific hypotheses formulated in Chapter One (Section 1.4.2), based on the findings discussed in the preceding sections. Using a combination of quantitative survey data, qualitative interviews with beneficiaries and key informants, and relevant literature, the hypotheses are verified through triangulated analysis.

The first hypothesis (H1) stated that there is a positive relationship between Green Amayaga Project participation and improved socio-economic outcomes for local communities in Kigoma Sector. The

evidence presented throughout Section 4.3 strongly supports this hypothesis. Approximately 68.52% of respondents reported increased household income, 70.37% cited improved farming productivity, and 64.81% experienced time-saving benefits due to the adoption of improved cookstoves. In-depth interviews further corroborated these findings, as many participants highlighted how income from public works (e.g., trench digging) and improved agricultural output helped them afford basic needs, including school fees and food. As one local leader noted, *“People got jobs digging terraces and planting trees and were paid. It helped them feed their families.”* These outcomes align with the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, which emphasizes that access to financial, physical, and natural capital contributes to sustainable well-being. Therefore, the first hypothesis is validated by both the numerical data and experiential testimonies from the field.

The second hypothesis (H2) proposed that the Green Amayaga Project has led to a positive shift in attitudes towards environmental conservation among participating community members. This hypothesis is also supported by the data. According to the survey results, over 95% of respondents reported an increase in their environmental awareness— 76 noted a “great increase,” while 22 noted a “slight increase.” Nearly all respondents (96.3%) indicated they now feel personally responsible for environmental protection. These attitudinal changes translated into practical behaviors, including planting and protecting trees (81.44%), using improved cookstoves (74.23%), and avoiding harmful practices like bush burning (70.10%).

Figure 9: Green Amayaga project impact verification

Source: Researcher own drawing , June ,2025.

Note: The up (↑) and down (↓) arrows are used as visual shorthand to indicate increases (positive outcomes) and decreases (challenges or negative outcomes) in relation to project impacts.

The third hypothesis (H3) stated that “limited community participation and poor follow-up significantly reduce the Green Amayaga Project’s effectiveness in promoting sustainable development”. The findings presented in Section 4.5 provide substantial support for this hypothesis. Although the project succeeded in reaching many households, there were significant implementation challenges that affected its inclusiveness and sustainability. Only 14.81% of respondents participated in training sessions, while others noted poor seedling survival due to a lack of follow-up and technical guidance. Several interviews highlighted gaps in coverage, particularly in villages like Kingina and Rugarama, which were excluded from key interventions such as tree planting and trench construction. Furthermore, complaints of inequitable distribution of goats, cookstoves, and fruit trees emerged, with some respondents alleging favoritism by local leaders. A beneficiary remarked, “*Some leaders gave resources only to their relatives. We were left out.*” These issues are consistent with existing literature, including studies by Kassa et al. (2022), which stress that limited follow-up, weak institutional coordination, and exclusion can undermine the long-term sustainability of restoration projects. Therefore, the third hypothesis is also confirmed by the evidence.

Chapter summary

This chapter presents key findings on socio-demographic characteristics, participation in project interventions, and the Green Amayaga Project’s socio-economic and environmental impacts. It shows notable gains in income, farming productivity, and energy access, with high adoption of improved cookstoves. It also confirms positive shifts in environmental attitudes but highlights implementation challenges such as inequity, low training coverage, and incomplete geographic reach. The hypotheses are verified through triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data. After presenting the findings and discussions based on field data, the next chapter is about general conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER V: GENERAL CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0. Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions derived from the findings discussed in Chapter Four and provides recommendations for improving the implementation and sustainability of future landscape restoration and rural development projects. The study aimed to evaluate the socio-economic and environmental impacts of the Green Amayaga Project in Kigoma Sector, with particular attention to community perceptions, project outcomes, and implementation challenges. The chapter is organized according to the study's research objectives and verified hypotheses.

5.1. Summary of the findings

The findings reveal that the Green Amayaga Project has had a significant positive impact on the socio-economic well-being of the participating households. A large majority of beneficiaries reported improvements in income, food security, and agricultural productivity. Key interventions such as agroforestry, soil conservation, goat distribution, and cookstove adoption contributed to increased household assets, labor efficiency, and cost savings. Approximately 68.52% of respondents reported increased household income, while 70.37% indicated improved farming output. These improvements were further supported by employment generated through public works like trench digging and terracing.

Moreover, the project contributed to broader well-being, as reflected in 62.96% of respondents rating its overall impact on their household as "very high." These outcomes confirm that integrated restoration and livelihood interventions can produce measurable benefits, particularly when supported by community engagement and local governance. However, the project's success was not equally distributed, and some participants reported minimal benefit due to lack of access to inputs or inadequate follow-up.

The project also succeeded in enhancing community awareness and attitudes towards environmental conservation. Over 95% of respondents indicated increased concern for environmental protection since the project began, and the majority reported adopting conservation practices such as tree planting, erosion control, and the use of clean cooking technologies. This transformation in environmental stewardship was fostered not only by the material interventions but also by effective mobilization methods, such as sports events, village meetings, and sensitization campaigns. These findings confirm that restoration projects can

create long-term behavioral change when they foster a sense of ownership and relevance among community members.

Despite the project's achievements, the study found several challenges that undermined its full potential. Some villages in Gahombo Cell, including Kingina and Rugarama, were excluded from major interventions due to limited resources. Only 14.81% of respondents reported receiving any training or capacity-building support, which weakened the sustainability of certain practices. Furthermore, inconsistent seedling follow-up, livestock damage to planted trees, and perceived favoritism in input distribution created mistrust and resentment in some areas. These issues underscore the importance of inclusive planning, robust monitoring, and equitable resource distribution.

The results support all three hypotheses set in Chapter One. The Green Amayaga Project has positively influenced socio-economic outcomes and attitudes toward environmental conservation, validating Hypotheses 1 and 2. However, the presence of substantial implementation challenges including limited participation, low training coverage, and poor follow-up also confirms Hypothesis 3, which warned that such weaknesses could hinder project effectiveness and sustainability.

5.3. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are categorized to address the roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders involved in the design, implementation, and sustainability of the Green Amayaga Project and similar future initiatives.

Recommendations to the Government and Policy Makers

1. Future restoration programs should ensure that all villages within targeted sectors are equitably covered. Villages such as Kingina and Rugarama were left out in this phase, reducing the inclusiveness and credibility of the intervention.
2. The government, through sector agronomists and decentralized structures, should strengthen routine field follow-up, ensuring proper maintenance of planted trees, trenches, and distributed livestock.

3. National restoration guidelines should require transparent and participatory criteria for selecting beneficiaries of goats, fruit trees, and training opportunities to prevent elite capture or favoritism at village level.
4. Formalize community-based environmental education and awareness in Imihigo (performance contracts) to ensure long-term conservation values are integrated into daily governance.

Recommendations to beneficiaries

1. Beneficiaries should recognize that trees, goats, and cookstoves are community assets. Active care and regular maintenance, such as watering seedlings and keeping livestock away from trees are crucial to long-term impact.
2. Households that received livestock or training should voluntarily share knowledge and resources (e.g., goat offspring) with others to build communal resilience and ensure wider reach.
3. Beneficiaries should participate actively in village assemblies or feedback channels to report challenges, suggest improvements, and enhance local accountability for project success.
4. Continued use of clean cookstoves, participation in tree planting, and avoidance of bush burning should become normalized community values, even after the project phase-out.

Recommendations to Research Institutions

1. Academic and technical institutions should support community-based monitoring systems where progress can be evaluated jointly with beneficiaries using simple indicators (e.g., tree survival, goat reproduction).
2. Universities and local researchers should help generate local case studies from successful interventions like in Birembo Village to inform similar projects in other regions.
3. Research institutions and sector agronomists should work together to design low-cost, practical training modules on tree care, sustainable farming, erosion control, and stove maintenance.
4. Leaders must ensure that project inputs are distributed fairly and communicate clearly with residents. Leadership integrity and trustworthiness are key to community acceptance and participation.

5.4. Areas for further research

This study focused on a single Village (Birembo) of Gahombo cell, within Kigoma Sector. Future research could:

- Conduct a comparative study across multiple sectors or districts to assess regional variations in project outcomes.
- Explore the long-term environmental effects (e.g., biodiversity recovery, carbon sequestration) of the Green Amayaga Project.
- Examine gender-specific impacts of restoration projects, especially regarding labor redistribution, income control, and decision-making.

Chapter summary

This concluding chapter synthesizes the study's main findings, affirming that the Green Amayaga Project has positively impacted household livelihoods and environmental stewardship in Kigoma Sector. However, it also stresses that certain limitations especially in coverage, training, and follow-up could undermine long-term sustainability. The chapter provides detailed recommendations for government, local leaders, beneficiaries, and research institutions. It also outlines areas for future research, such as long-term environmental monitoring and gender-focused analyses. These conclusions highlight the need for continued policy attention and scholarly engagement to improve the design and scalability of FLR initiatives across Rwanda.

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APPENDIX

Survey Questionnaire

Note: Only eligible respondents (aged 18+, direct beneficiaries, residents of Birembo Village since 3 years before 2020, and voluntarily participating) are to be interviewed. The questionnaire is structured to align with the study's specific objectives.

Section A: Respondent Profile (Demographic Information)

1. Age group

- 18 – 35 years
- 36 – 52 years
- 53 above

2. Gender

- Male Female Other

1. Marital Status

- Single
Married
Widowed
Divorced/Separated

3. Main livelihood activity

- Crop farming
 Livestock farming
 Trading
 Paid employment

 High school student

 University Student

4. **Level of education:**

- No formal education
- Primary
- Secondary
- Tertiary
- Vocational training

Section B: Socio-Economic Benefits

6. Which Green Amayaga Project activities did you participate in? Which project activities did you benefit from? (Tick all that apply)

- Tree planting
- Agroforestry
- Improved cookstove use
- Soil conservation
- Training/workshops

Received Goats

- Other (specify): _____

7. Since participating, have you experienced any of the following benefits? (Tick all that apply)

- Increase in household income
- Access to cleaner energy (e.g., cookstoves)
- Improved farming productivity
- Time-saving in daily tasks because of stoves
- Better access to food or nutrition
- No noticeable benefit

Paying school fees

- Other (please explain): _____

8. How would you rate the project's contribution to your household's well-being?

- Very high
- Moderate
- Low
- No contribution

9. Briefly describe any new skills or knowledge you gained from the project

.....

.....

.....

.....

Section C: Attitudes Toward Environmental Conservation

10. How has the project influenced your concern for environmental conservation?

- Increased greatly
- Increased slightly
- No change
- Decreased

11. In your daily life, which practices do you now follow to help conserve the environment? (Tick all that apply)

- Planting and protecting trees
- Avoiding bush burning or deforestation
- Using improved cookstoves
- Teaching others about environmental care
- Managing soil erosion or runoff
- None

12. Do you feel a personal responsibility to protect the environment after your involvement in the project?

- Yes

No

Not sure

Please explain why: _____

.....
.....

Section D: Challenges Facing the Project

13. What challenges have you experienced in continuing the practices promoted by the project?.....
.....
.....

14. What do you think should be improved if the Green Amayaga Project continues or expands?
.....
.....
.....

Section E: Open Feedback (Optional)

15. Do you have any other comments, stories, or suggestions about your experience with the project?.....
.....
.....

Interview guides

Key Informant Interview Guide

Target: Project ma, local Executive Secretary, Agronomist, Forestry Officer)

1. What were the main objectives of the Green Amayaga Project in this community?
2. How were the target beneficiaries identified and engaged?
3. What socio-economic changes have you observed in the community?
4. How have community attitudes toward the environment changed over time?
5. What are the major implementation challenges you have encountered?
6. What role have local institutions and leaders played in supporting the project?
7. What lessons or best practices can be drawn from this intervention?
8. How sustainable are the project outcomes without ongoing external funding?

In-Depth Interview Guide (for Selected Active Beneficiaries)

Purpose: To gather detailed narratives about individual experiences and perceived impact.

1. How did you first get involved in the Green Amayaga Project?
2. Which activities have you participated in, and what motivated you?
3. Can you describe any changes you have experienced in your livelihood?
4. Have these changes affected your daily life or long-term plans?
5. How do you now view your role in conserving the environment?
6. What difficulties have you faced in applying what you learned from the project?
7. What would you want to see improved if the project were to continue or expand?

D. Observation Checklist

Purpose: To validate physical, on-the-ground indicators of implementation.

Observation Item	Yes	No	Notes/Description
Tree planting is visible (e.g., on hilltops, farms)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Agroforestry practices in use (e.g., intercropping)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Soil erosion control (terraces, trenches, contours)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Improved cook stoves in households	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Evidence of community environmental awareness posters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Any signs of project-based infrastructure deterioration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Livelihood assets visibly improved (e.g., new crops/animals)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	